

Academic Self- Efficacy and Achievement Motivation as Predictors of University Academic Success: A Pilot Study

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to assess the predictive power of academic self-efficacy and achievement motivation on university students' achievement (FYCGPA) among 4th year university students. It specifically investigates age and gender/sex- related patterns of achievement in university based on a randomly drawn sample of 208 (male = 141 and female = 67) from a total population of 333 medicine and health sciences college 4th year students (male= 185, female = 148) in Hawassa university. The adapted scales of academic self-efficacy, and achievement motivation were employed to collect data. Students' university achievement was measured based on first year cumulative GPA (FYCGPA). The adapted scales yielded acceptable internal consistency reliabilities ranging from 0.86 - 0.90 and statistically significant convergent and discriminant validity coefficients between the two scales ($r = .47, p < .001$). Hierarchical and simultaneous multiple regression procedures were used to address the major research questions. The findings revealed that academic self-efficacy (ASE) and achievement motivation (AM) are strong predictors of university students' achievement when used jointly. When used separately, AM was identified as better predictor of university students' achievement as compared to ASE. On the other hand, university students' achievement (FYCGPA) is significantly predicted by Age and Gender/Sex. Low achievement in university among 4th year students is associated more with girls than boys. Besides, a declining trend in university students' achievement is also evident with increasing age. Finally, the study outlines the implications of the findings.

Key Words: Academic self-efficacy, Academic success, Achievement motivation, Ethiopia, Predictors, University

INTRODUCTION

Background of the problem

According to previous and contemporary literatures, admission requirements include both cognitive and non-cognitive variables (Yousafzai & Jamil, 2019). Variables such as secondary school certificate, high school transcript average, standardized exams, and admission aptitude test scores are among the cognitive elements (Liu et al., 2018). However, they are insufficient on their own to determine whether pupils should be admitted to schools and universities. They therefore serve as imperfect indicators of how well a student will perform in university-level curriculum. Non-cognitive variables, on the other hand, include psychological variables such as academic self-efficacy and achievement motivation in addition to socio-demographic variables such as age, gender, and experience, among others. Similarly, recent years researchers in education and social sciences have recognized that non-cognitive factors and skills play a crucial role in educational success and achievement (Stankov & Lee, 2014; Barrett, 2014). They firmly believe that non-cognitive factors and skills are equally or even more important than cognitive aspects in educative process and employment potential. Increasing attempts are being made to investigate the role of non-cognitive factors and how they associate with academic success. Thus, these and other related findings clearly reveal that there is a need to use non-cognitive predictors in addition to cognitive predictors for admission purpose.

On the other hand, according to Diaz Lema et al. (2023) one of the main objectives of higher education is to increase the percentage of young people with university degrees. This needs actions that make it possible for students not only to access university, but also to successfully complete it (Roberts, 2011). Besides, higher education institutions must make considerable efforts – based on the latest research results – to reduce dropout rates and, at the same time, accelerate admission rates while continuously improving completion rates, which are among the lowest in the OECD (OECD, 2017).

Academic success can be described as a complex web of factors that involve personal, academic, organizational, pedagogical and social dimensions (e.g. Alyahyan & Düşteğör, 2020; Diaz Lema et al., 2023) and interact with and influence each other (York, Gibson, & Rankin, 2015). These predictors are important as they provide insights into an individual's potential for academic performance and success in higher institutions.

Academic success is most commonly operationalized as students' first-year grade point average (GPA) as well as final undergraduate GPA, and the effectiveness of selection variables may differ between first-year GPA and final GPA. The first year in university is a critical transition period as it is a time when students lay the foundation on which their subsequent academic success and persistence rest. Different classifications of predictors of academic success exist (Alyahyan & Düşteğör, 2020; Van Rooij, Jansen, & van de Grift, 2018), but they can basically be divided into two parts: cognitive and non-cognitive predictors. The most commonly studied cognitive predictors are grade point average (GPA) and prior academic achievement (PAA) measured by grades and standardized tests (e.g. Li & Wong, 2019; Naaman, 2021; Van Herpen et al., 2020; Richardson, Abraham, Bond, 2012; Westrick et al., 2021) provided they are used as an indicator of academic success and aptitude to perform academic task.

The most commonly monitored non-cognitive predictors of academic success in higher education are socio-economic factors (SES), learning and self-regulation strategies, and motivational factors, such as goal orientation and self-efficacy (e.g., Musso, Rodríguez-Hernández, & Cascallar, 2020; Rodríguez-Hernández et al., 2021; Aldhabi & Karpinski, 2020; Farruggia et al., 2018; Ribeiro et al., 2019; Alban & Mauricio, 2019; Behr et al., 2010; Bowles & Brindle, 2017; Ndoye, Clarke, & Henderson, 2020; Rump, Esdar, & Wild, 2017; Vanthournout et al., 2012).

Academic self-efficacy refers to one's expectation of his ability to perform academic tasks acceptably. In other words, academic self-efficacy refers to one's actual ability in various academic topics of a specialization (Abdulnaser, F. & Laith, H.H., 2022). It is operationally measured by the score that a student achieves after responding to the items of the academic self-efficacy scales. Academic self-efficacy is influenced by various variables such as the number of individuals in an academic department, ages of students, and level of academic willingness for academic achievement (Dabi, 2017; Al-Johuria & Al-Zufairi, 2019; Karwowski & Koufman, 2017).

Similarly, numerous other researches and meta-analyses show that academic self-efficacy and academic performance have a well-established positive link over and beyond other variables like cognitive ability and high school academic performance (Komarraju & Nadler, 2013; Lee, Lee, & Bong, 2014). It is also possible through self-efficiency to predict whether a student has a high or low level of academic achievement (Kirmash, 2016). In addition, self-efficacy has a direct impact on behavioral and thinking patterns, on the grounds that the thoughts of an individual can either be positive or negative (Rumaisa, 2017). Moreover, another research conducted on academic self-efficacy suggests that it is a strong non-cognitive factor in academic success outcomes, and it has sound theoretical and practical implications (Ashley, 2014). Furthermore, various studies have shown there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic achievement (Abdulnaser, F. & Laith H. H., 2022; Byrne et al, 2014; Chairiyati, 2013; Phan, 2010; Sari & Mariah, 2017).

On the other hand, previous and contemporary research suggests that academic motivation is a significant non-cognitive component to academic performance, even more so than cognitive ability (Amrai, Motlagh, Zalani, & Parhon, 2011; Vecchione, Alessandri, & Marsicano, 2014). The self-determination theory (SDT), which identifies the various impulses toward task engagement, is the theoretical foundation for the idea that academic motivation is rooted in people's intrinsic propensity to express their interests, activate and develop their potentials, and overcome obstacles. Achievement motivation is a motivation to achieve a stable learned characteristic in which a person obtains satisfaction by striving for and attaining a level of excellence (Nwankwo, Obi & Agu, 2013). That means high level of achievement motivation leads to better performance in learning process. In addition, it was also found that there is a significant positive relationship between achievement motivation and academic self-efficacy (Peter O. Olapegba, Peter O. Famakinde & Ijeoma C. Njoku, 2017)

In this regard Ethiopia has its own experience of applying admission procedures to admit students at college and university level. At university level, the current experience in Ethiopia shows that selection of eligible students has been exclusively relied on scores of National University Entrance Exam held at the end of grade 12. This experience clearly shows that only a small portion of cognitive predictors has been used as a component of admission criterion to select students for higher institutions. Thus, there is a need to use non-cognitive predictors/psychological variables/ in addition to cognitive predictors in order to get competent students.

Regarding to demographic variables such as age and gender, some studies concluded that there is negative relationship between age and academic achievement (Cecilia et al., 2019; Ünal, 2019; Jabor et al., 2011). However, the study conducted by Nasir (2012) revealed that increase in age brings improvement in academic performance. On the other hand, according to the findings of various researches conducted on gender disparities, men outperformed women on arithmetic exams while women outperformed men on verbal ability and accomplishment tests (Delaney& Devereux, 2021; Cecilia et al., 2019; Fortes, Rodrigues & Tchanchane, 2010). Besides, the research conducted by Ifdil et al. (2016) about the level of students' self-efficacy showed that self-efficacy between males and females had a significant difference. Moreover, the study conducted by Akpan and Umobong (2013) found that gender had a significant influence on achievement motivation of students, with males being more highly motivated than females. However, the study conducted by Abd et al. (2020) showed that male and female students do not have significant differences related to their academic self-efficacy.

Statement of the problem

The selection of students who demonstrate a higher probability of successful academic performance in training program is the goal of most selection and admission criteria. To achieve this goal, there is always a need to use valid and reliable admission criteria to screen students for higher institutions. In addition, selection of students should be based on a variety of assessment procedures to maximize the possibility of choosing the best candidates with respect to cognitive and non-cognitive qualities and promotion of social inclusion (Ezeala et al., 2012). Moreover, there is considerable evidence that supports the use of psychological variables such as academic self-efficacy and achievement motivation as complementary to the traditional criteria (which use only cognitive predictors) to predict students' success at university (Stankov & Lee, 2014; Barrett, 2014).

However, the current experience in Ethiopia shows that selection of eligible students for university has been based only on the scores of National University Entrance Exam held at the end of grade 12. This experience clearly shows that only a small portion of cognitive predictors has been used as a component of admission criterion to select students for higher institutions. Thus, this gap clearly reveals that there is a need to use non-cognitive predictors/psychological variables/ in addition to cognitive predictors in order to get competent students for future. Furthermore, the effects of age and gender on the predictive validity of psychological variables have also been examined. In this regard, this study is aimed at assessing the predictive power of psychological variables (Academic Self-Efficacy and Achievement Motivation) in predicting university academic success. More specifically, the study is intended to find answers for the following research questions.

1. To what extent Academic Self-Efficacy (ASE) predicts the First Year Cumulative GPA (FYCGPA) in the university?
2. To what extent Achievement Motivation (AM) predicts the First Year Cumulative GPA (FYCGPA) in the university?
3. Do age and gender influence university academic success as measured by the First Year Cumulative GPA (FYCGPA)?
4. What is the predictive validity of each of the predictor variables?

Significance of the Study

As far as the knowledge of the researcher is concerned, few researches have been conducted so far in an attempt to consider non-cognitive predictor variables when conducting predictive validity study in the Ethiopian context. This gap clearly reveals that there is a need to include both cognitive and non-cognitive predictors in the study regarding the predictive validity of admission criteria to select students for higher institutions. Thus, the findings of this study can be valuable in guiding admissions personnel and decision-makers at the Ministry of Education in identifying whether psychological variables such as academic self-efficacy and achievement motivation are accurate predictors of academic success of students attending higher institutions.

Scope of the Study

The main focus of this study is assessing the predictive power of academic self-efficacy and achievement motivation in predicting university academic success in the Ethiopian context. As a pilot study, medicine and health sciences college of Hawassa university was selected randomly to take sample for the study. Besides, the effect of age and gender on university academic success was also examined.

METHODOLOGY

The study design, target population and sampling techniques, development and adaptation of the data gathering tools and the methods of data analyses employed are discussed as follows.

Study Design

This study utilized the correlational research design using the survey technique. The study specifically focuses on 4th year university students in a randomly selected medicine and health sciences college, in Hawassa university, one of the first-generation universities in Ethiopia.

Target Population and Sampling techniques

The sample was randomly drawn from a total population of 333 medicine and health sciences college students (male= 185, female = 148) in Hawassa university. Of the 220 (142 males and 78 females) respondents randomly selected to participate in the study, 208 of them returned completed questionnaires. Finally, 208 (141 males and 67 females) were considered in the data analysis.

Instruments of Data Gathering

The study employed adapted scales of academic self-efficacy, and achievement motivation. Biographical information on the respondents was obtained with the help of a questionnaire administered along with the adapted scales. Data on students' first year achievement were obtained from students' individual self-report. The details on the instrument adaptation and validation process are given as follows.

Adapting the Academic Self-Efficacy (Chemers et al., 2001) Scale

For the purpose of the present study, the Chemers et al. (2001) academic self-efficacy scale was adapted by the researcher. The original scale consists of 8 items on a 7-point Likert-type scale from 1 (Very Untrue) to 7 (Very True). Points 2 thru 6 were not labeled. Participants were asked to rate on a 1 to 7 scale how well they believe they perform certain academic tasks. Participants were asked questions such as "I know how to schedule my time to accomplish my tasks." Chemers et

al. (2001) obtained a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of .81 for the scale in their study of 373 undergraduates. The Adapted academic self-efficacy scale consisted of nine items measured in a five-point Likert-type scale rated from 1 (Very Untrue) to 5 (Very True). The internal consistency reliability of the adapted scale was found to be high ($\alpha=.86$) which was greater than that of the original scale ($\alpha=.81$).

Adapting the Achievement Motivation (Vallerand et al., 1992) Scale

The original scale includes 28 items and 7 factors, each factor includes 4 items, and each item has 7 response categories. The scale consists of 3 intrinsic motivation factors, 3 extrinsic motivation factors, and one factor of amotivation. These factors are intrinsic motivation - to know, intrinsic motivation - toward accomplishment, intrinsic motivation - to experience stimulation, extrinsic motivation - identified, extrinsic motivation - introjected, extrinsic motivation - external regulation and amotivation. Amotivation is a single dimension measured with four items. It is characterized by an individual's lack of purpose, an absence of power over their actions, or explains an inability to act. The original study conducted by Vallerand et al. (1992) found Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the seven-factor structure ranging between 0.83 and 0.86. The Adapted academic motivation scale consisted of 28 items measured in a five-point Likert-type scale rated from 1 (Does not correspond at all) to 5 (Corresponds exactly). The internal consistency reliability of the adapted scale for total scale was found to be high ($\alpha=.90$) which was greater than that of the original scale ($\alpha=.86$). Eventually, the total number of items for the adapted total scale was reduced to 23 since five of the items were discarded owing to very low total-item correlation ($r=.17$ to $r=.21$).

Reliability and Validity Evidence

The two scales (ASE and AM) and other background factors included in the questionnaire were made available to the dissertation supervisors and two educational measurement and evaluation psychologists from the university. All expert comments were duly noted and taken into account to improve the tools prior to conducting the study. As indicated above, the internal consistency reliability for both adapted scales were found to be ($\alpha=.86$) and ($\alpha=.90$), respectively. Then after, both convergent and discriminant validity evidences were established using bivariate correlations between the two adapted measures of ASE and AM by the researcher.

- ***University Students' Achievement (USAch):*** USAch was captured based on their first year cumulative GPA (FYCGPA) of the 2020/2021 academic year. The data were obtained from student self-reports included in the questionnaire.

Procedures of Data Analysis

Data analysis for this study included both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was computed for predictor variables (Age, Sex, ASES, and AMS) and for the criterion variable (first-year CGPA). In descriptive analysis, mean scores, standard deviations, maximum and minimum values of the predictor and criterion variables were determined to show the general picture of the data. Then, analysis of relationships of variables was done. Initially, Pearson correlation coefficients were computed among predictor variables. Then, it was computed between each predictor and criterion variables.

In Inferential statistics, standard (stepwise) multiple regression and hierarchical multiple regression were chosen as statistical methods. Standard multiple regression was employed to

examine the extent to which predictor variables (Age, Sex, ASES, and AMS) collectively and separately contributed in predicting criterion variable (university academic performance as measured by first year CGPA). Because, standard multiple regression analysis provides the proportion of explained variance, also known as the coefficient of determination or R^2 in the criterion variable (first year University CGPA) that is accounted for or explained by the combined predictor variables (Age, Sex, ASES, and AMS). At the same time, the analysis results provided standardized regression coefficients of each predictor variable which is an indicator of the relative prediction power of the predictor variables. Based on this information, the beta weight was determined to each of the predictor variables. In regression analysis, the following prediction equation or model is often used:

$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + e$ where ‘Y’ is the predicted or dependent variable, ‘X1’ is the score on the first predictor variable (Age), ‘X2’ is the score on the second predictor variable (Sex), ‘X3’ is the score on the third predictor variable (ASES), ‘X4’ is the score on the fourth predictor variable (AMS), and ‘a’ is the constant or intercept, representing the amount that the dependent variable will be when all the independent variables are zero. The regression coefficients ($\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$) represent the amount that criterion variable (first year CGPA) changes when the corresponding predictor variable changes one unit, all other factors held constant. Finally, ‘e’ stands for prediction error or statistical noise (the difference between observed value and predicted value of the dependent variable). F-test and t-test was used respectively to examine whether the joint and individual contribution of predictor variables in predicting a criterion variable is statistically significant.

Hierarchical multiple regression analysis was employed to examine whether the addition of ASES, and AMS up on Age and Sex scores improves the prediction of first year university academic performance. In this study, hierarchical regression has three blocks since age and sex are entered collectively in model 1 though there are four predictor variables. Hence, score of Age and Sex, ASES, and AMS was entered in these regression blocks- Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3 respectively. This order-of-entry feature, where some predictors are considered before looking at others, is what makes this a “hierarchical” regression procedure – some variables take precedence in the hierarchy over others. Moreover, before applying multiple regressions as data analysis method, assumptions of i.e., Normality, Linearity, Independent of errors, Homoscedasticity, etc. were checked in order to assess the validity of the model.

Ethical issues

Informed consent to conduct this study was obtained from college of education, research ethics committee in Hawassa university, and informed consent to participate in the study was obtained from participant students. Prior to filling the questionnaire, participating students were given orientations about the purpose of the study and the procedures of the questionnaire. The researcher confirmed to the students that the information given by the students will only be used confidentially for research purposes. The students were also told that if they did not want to participate in the questionnaire, they had the absolute right not to take it and could even interrupt during the questionnaire.

DATA ANALYSIS

Before running the final statistical analyses, preliminary cross-tabulations and frequency analysis were carried out for all variables in the questionnaire. Accordingly, variables with incorrect data,

and cases with missing values were identified. Errors during data entry were corrected while cases with missing values were excluded from the final analysis. In addition, the assumptions of multiple regression analysis were also checked before applying the model. The remaining sample size following the removal of cases with missing values was sufficiently large ($n = 208$) to run the analyses. Then, data interpretation was made using descriptive statistics, one-sample t-test, bivariate correlations, standard and hierarchical multiple regression analyses.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

This section attempts to answer the research questions mentioned above. In doing so, first answering the questions 1 and 2: To what extent Academic Self-Efficacy (ASE) and Achievement Motivation (AM) predict the First Year Cumulative GPA (FYCGPA) in the university? The analysis used university 4th year students as a reference.

Assessing the predictive power of psychological variables (ASE and AM) on university academic success as measured by FYCGPA

As reported earlier, randomly selected university 4th year students from the target population were asked about their Academic Self-Efficacy (ASE) and Achievement Motivation (AM). Table 2 and 3 present summaries of the results for both scales separately.

By employing the adapted version of the Academic Self-Efficacy (ASE) scale, the researcher asked respondents to rate their level of confidence to successfully perform 9 academic tasks in university. To answer the key research question: “How confident are university students in performing academic tasks?” students’ observed mean scores on each ASE item was compared against set criteria (set as “confident” = 4). In SPSS language it is called “test value”, but in statistical literature it is known as population mean: $\mu=4$ (meaning, “I am confident”). Table 1 presents result of academic self-efficacy.

Table 1

Academic self-efficacy (ASE) among university 4th year students

(Test Value = 4: I am confident), N = 208

No.	<i>To what extent you are confident to perform the following university academic tasks?</i>	Mean ^a	SD	t
1	I know how to schedule my time to accomplish my tasks.	3.80	.98	-2.90**
2	I understand how to take notes.	3.98	.98	-.28(ns)
3	I understand how to study in order to perform well on tests.	3.97	.89	-.54(ns)
4	I am good at research and writing papers.	3.14	1.12	-11.10***
5	I am an excellent student.	3.61	1.03	-5.43***
6	I usually do very well in university and at academic tasks.	3.73	.92	-4.32***
7	My university academic work fascinates me.	3.33	1.92	-8.10***
8	My university academic work motivates me.	4.01	1.04	.20(ns)
9	I am confident in my ability to succeed at the university.	3.26	1.24	-8.62***

** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$; ns=not significant

Notes: *“The observed means of Academic Self-Efficacy (ASE) items were compared against a specified mean (or test value) =4 (“I am confident”).*

As can be evident from Table 1, the observed mean scores of all the ASE items except for item 8 were found to be less than four (which was set as criteria for comparison). This is evident from the negative t values. However, of the nine items, students’ mean scores are particularly low for six out of the nine ASE items. These were: “I know how to schedule my time to accomplish my tasks” (M = 3.80; SD = .98, t = -2.90, p < .01), “I am good at research and writing papers” (M = 3.14; SD = 1.12, t = -11.10, p < .001), “I am an excellent student” (M = 3.61; SD = 1.03, t = -5.43, p < .001), “I usually do very well in university and at academic tasks” (M = 3.73; SD = .92, t = -4.32, p < .001), “My university academic work fascinates me” (M = 3.33; SD = 1.92, t = -8.10, p < .001), and “I am confident in my ability to succeed at the university” (M = 3.26; SD = 1.24, t = -8.62, p < .001). On the other hand, on the remaining three items: “I understand how to take notes” (M = 3.98, SD = .98, t = -.28, ns), “I understand how to study in order to perform well on tests.” (M = 3.97; SD = .89, t = -.54, ns), and “My university academic work motivates me” (M = 4.01, SD = 1.04, t = 0.20, ns), the observed means did not differ significantly from the criterion score (i.e., 4 or “confident”). This generally suggests that the average university 4th year students are more or less confident to successfully solve three out of nine university academic tasks. As such, it can safely be concluded that the average (or typical) university 4th year students have low ASE in the target population. Similarly, Table 2 presents result of achievement motivation.

Table 2*Achievement Motivation (AM) among university 4th year students***(Test Value = 4: "Correspondence"), N = 208**

No.	WHY DO YOU GO TO UNIVERSITY?	Mean ^b	SD	t
1	To experience pleasure and satisfaction while learning new things.	3.58	1.21	-5.05***
2	Because I think that a university education will help me better prepare for the career I have chosen.	3.90	1.12	-1.24(ns)
3	For the deep feelings I experience when I am communicating my own ideas to others.	3.27	1.25	-8.44***
4	For the pleasure I experience while surpassing myself in my studies.	3.02	1.27	-11.10***
5	To prove to myself that I am capable of completing my university degree.	3.47	1.30	-5.94***
6	In order to obtain a more prestigious job later on.	3.79	1.11	-2.75**
7	For the pleasure I experience when I discover new things I have never seen before.	3.54	1.21	-5.46***
8	Because eventually it will enable me to enter the job market in a field that I like.	3.50	1.21	-5.97***
9	For the pleasure that I experience when I read interesting authors.	3.08	1.33	-9.97***
10	For the pleasure that I experience while I am surpassing myself in one of my personal accomplishments.	3.42	1.13	-7.39***
11	Because when I succeed in university, I feel important.	3.62	1.17	-4.73***
12	Because I want to have "the good life" later on.	3.88	1.11	-1.56(ns)
13	For the pleasure that I experience in broadening my knowledge about subjects which appeal to me.	3.77	1.17	-2.84**
14	Because this will help me make a better choice regarding my career orientation.	3.68	1.11	-4.14***
15	For the pleasure that I experience when I feel completely absorbed by what certain authors have written.	2.99	1.21	-12.02***
16	For the satisfaction I feel when I am in the process of accomplishing difficult academic activities.	3.25	1.21	-8.91***
17	To show myself that I am an intelligent person.	3.60	1.18	-4.94***
18	In order to have a better salary later on.	3.52	1.26	-5.49***
19	Because my studies allow me to continue to learn about many things that interest me.	3.19	1.31	-8.97***
20	Because I believe that a few additional years of education will improve my competence as a worker.	3.70	1.13	-3.81***
21	For the "high" feeling that I experience while reading about various interesting subjects.	3.29	1.25	-8.25***
22	Because university allows me to experience a personal satisfaction in my desire for excellence in my studies.	3.39	1.22	-7.14***
23	Because I want to show myself that I can succeed in my studies.	3.64	1.22	-4.26***

** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

Notes: ^bThe observed mean of Achievement Motivation (AM) items were compared against a specified mean (Test value) = 4 (“Correspondence”)

As can be seen from Table 2, the observed mean scores of all the AM items were found to be less than four (which was set as criteria for comparison). This is clearly observed from the negative t values. Besides, of the twenty-three items, students’ mean scores are differently low for nineteen out of the twenty-three AM items. These were: “To experience pleasure and satisfaction while learning new things” (M = 3.58; SD = 1.21, t = -5.05, p < .001), “For the deep feelings I experience when I am communicating my own ideas to others” (M = 3.27; SD = 1.25, t = -8.44, p < .001), “For the pleasure I experience while surpassing myself in my studies” (M = 3.02; SD = 1.27, t = -11.10, p < .001), “To prove to myself that I am capable of completing my university degree” (M = 3.47; SD = 1.30, t = -5.94, p < .001), “For the pleasure I experience when I discover new things I have never seen before” (M = 3.54; SD = 1.21, t = -5.46, p < .001), “Because eventually it will enable me to enter the job market in a field that I like” (M = 3.50; SD = 1.21, t = -5.97, p < .001), “For the pleasure that I experience when I read interesting authors” (M=3.08; SD=1.33, t=-9.97, p < .001), “For the pleasure that I experience while I am surpassing myself in one of my personal accomplishments” (M=3.42; SD=1.13, t=-7.39, p < .001), “Because when I succeed in university, I feel important” (M=3.62; SD=1.17, t=-4.73, p < .001), “Because this will help me make a better choice regarding my career orientation” (M=3.68; SD=1.11, t=-4.14), p < .001, “For the pleasure that I experience when I feel completely absorbed by what certain authors have written” (M=2.99; SD=1.21, t= -12.02, p < .001), “For the satisfaction I feel when I am in the process of accomplishing difficult academic activities” (M=3.25; SD=1.21, t=-8.91, p < .001), “To show myself that I am an intelligent person” (M=3.60; SD=1.18, t=-4.94, p < .001), “In order to have a better salary later on” (M=3.52; SD=1.26, t=-5.49, p < .001), “Because my studies allow me to continue to learn about many things that interest me” (M=3.19; SD=1.31, t=-8.97, p < .001), “Because I believe that a few additional years of education will improve my competence as a worker” (M=3.70; SD=1.13, t=-3.81, p < .001), “For the “high” feeling that I experience while reading about various interesting subjects” (M=3.29; SD=1.25, t=-8.25, p < .001), “Because university allows me to experience a personal satisfaction in my desire for excellence in my studies” (M=3.39; SD=1.22, t=-7.14, p < .001), and “Because I want to show myself that I can succeed in my studies” (M=3.64; SD=1.22, t=-4.26, p < .001).

On the other hand, of the remaining four items, two of them: “In order to obtain a more prestigious job later on” (M = 3.79; SD = 1.11, t = -2.75, p < .01), and “For the pleasure that I experience in broadening my knowledge about subjects which appeal to me” (M = 3.77; SD = 1.17, t = -2.84, p < .01) are more or less good than the mentioned ones above. The remaining two: “Because I think that a university education will help me better prepare for the career I have chosen” (M = 3.90, SD = 1.12, t = -1.24, ns), and “Because I want to have “the good life” later on” (M=3.88; SD=1.11, t=-1.56, ns) are better than all others as their observed means did not differ significantly from the criterion score (i.e., 4 or “correspondence”). This generally suggests that the average university 4th year students are less reasonable to join university since only two reasons out of twenty-three options have got correspondence. Thus, it can safely be concluded that the average (or typical) university 4th year students have lower-level justification for joining university in the target population. Table 3 presents descriptive statistics and inter-correlations of the study variables.

Table 3*Mean, SD, and Inter-correlations of the study variables*

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	SD
1. Age	-	.07	-.02	.00	-.24**	24.50	1.60
2. Sex	.07	-	-.10	-.11	.13	.68	.47
3. ASE	-.02	-.10	-	.47**	.02	3.64	.72
4. AM	.00	-.11	.47**	-	-.20**	3.36	.66
5. FYCGPA	-.24**	.13	.02	-.20**	-	3.47	.24

** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Notes: ASE = Academic Self-Efficacy, AM = Achievement Motivation, and FYCGPA = First Year Cumulative GPA

Inter-correlation among the study Variables

The inter-correlation results (as observed in Table 3 above) show the bivariate linear relationships among the key variables of interest for which there exists some empirical or theoretical background. The results suggest that students' age and sex represent distinct patterns of relationships with ASE, AM, and FYCGPA. Specifically, age has significant negative correlation only with FYCGPA ($r = -.24$, $p < .01$). On the other hand, sex has no significant relationship with FYCGPA, ASE and AM. Besides, FYCGPA correlated negatively and significantly with AM ($r = -.20$, $p < .01$). Moreover, strong positive relationship was observed between ASE and AM ($r = .47$, $p < .01$). Overall, from the bivariate correlations, it is possible to identify which predictors may be selected for further multivariate analysis with the help of simultaneous and hierarchical procedures of multiple regression analyses. In particular, the preference for hierarchical multiple regression analysis was based on its inherent advantage of controlling the effect of other independent variables except the variables of interest (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013)

Predictors of university students' achievement as measured by FYCGPA from the study variables

According to the existing empirical and theoretical literature, university students' achievement is influenced by cognitive or non-cognitive factors such as academic self-efficacy and achievement motivation as well as demographic variables such as age and sex (e.g. Eccles & Roeser, 2011; Jabor et al., 2011; Arhin & Offoe, 2015; Ayob & Yasin, 2017). In view of these, the key question raised above need to be addressed: *To what extent Academic Self-Efficacy (ASE) and Achievement Motivation (AM) predict the First Year Cumulative GPA (FYCGPA) in university?* To answer this research question, both hierarchical and standard multiple regression analyses were computed. To find out the level of importance of non-cognitive predictors (ASE and AM) in predicting university students' achievement as measured by FYCGPA when the effects of other covariates (age and sex) are controlled, hierarchical multiple regression in three steps would need to be fitted to the data. Similarly, in the process of assessing the level of importance of non-cognitive predictors (ASE and AM), the third research question: *Do age and sex influence university academic success as measured by the First Year Cumulative GPA (FYCGPA)?* was also addressed in the same table as depicted below. Table 5 presents hierarchical regression for university students' achievement.

Table 4*Hierarchical regression for university students' achievement*

Model	Variables	B	SE	β	R^2	adj R^2	ΔR^2	F	ΔF	r	pr^2	sr^2
1	Age	-.04	.01	-.25***						-.24	-.25	-.25
	Sex	.07	.03	.14*	.077	.068	.077	8.52***	8.52***	.13	.15	.14
2	Age	-.04	.01	-.25***						-.24	-.25	-.25
	Sex	.07	.03	.15*						.13	.14	.13
	ASE	.01	.02	.03(ns)	.078	.064	.001	5.73***	.20(ns)	.02	.03	.03
3	Age	-.04	.01	-.24***						-.24	-.25	-.24
	Sex	.07	.03	.13*						.13	-.26	-.23
	ASE	.05	.02	.15*						.02	.14	.13
	AM	-.09	.03	.25***	.127	.110	.050	7.41***	11.57***	-.20	-.23	-.22

* $p < .05$, *** $p < .001$, (ns)-not significant

Note: (a) The multiple regression analysis is free of multicollinearity problem since "Tolerance" statistics (.72 to .99) considerably larger than .10 while the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) in all cases are below 10, which will be a cause for concern (Pallant, 2010, p. 158); $DB=1.57$ to 1.65

(b) In the far-right columns the symbols: pr^2 represents the partial correlation while sr^2 represents the Semi-partial correlation of individual predictors

As shown in Table 4 above, in Model I, the effects of "Age" and "Sex" on university students' achievement (FYCGPA) were evaluated controlling for the effects of other covariates (or IV): ASE and AM. As it is evident, "Sex" ($\beta = .14$, $p < .05$; $sr^2 = .14$) emerged as a statistically significant predictor of university students' achievement (FYCGPA). Similarly, "Age" ($\beta = -.25$, $p < .001$; $sr^2 = .25$) was also emerged as a statistically significant predictor of university students' achievement (FYCGPA). However, the negative regression coefficient shows that as age increases the achievement of students decreases. Model I, which constituted the two variables contributes about 7.7% ($R^2 = .077$) of the variance in university students' achievement (FYCGPA). The introduction of Academic Self-Efficacy (ASE: $\beta = .03$, $p > .05$) in Model II though yielding non-significant predictive relationship with university students' achievement (FYCGPA), it has increased the overall percentage of variance ($R^2 = .078$, contributing about 0.1%, $\Delta R^2 = .001$, $p > .05$) additional variance to the overall prediction. The inclusion of Achievement Motivation (AM: $\beta = .25$, $p < .001$) in Model III, increases the effect of ASE ($\beta = .15$, $sr^2 = .13$) on university students' achievement (FYCGPA) and moved up the proportion of variance explained by the model with an additional variance of 5% ($\Delta R^2 = .050$, $p < .001$). In sum, university students' achievement (FYCGPA) among 4th year students is strongly predicted by student age, sex, ASE, and AM contributing about 12.7% (adj $R^2 = .110$) of the variance. In other words, low achievement in

university students' achievement (FYCGPA) among 4th year students is associated more with girls than boys, and students with low academic self-efficacy, and low achievement motivation.

Table 5 presents Summary of multiple regression analysis.

Table 5

Summary of multiple regression analysis predicting university students' achievement (FYCGPA)

Model	Variables	Multiple correlation and its related values			Values in the stepwise regression	
		R	R ²	Change in R ²	β	F
1	Age	.237	.056	.056	-.24	12.25***
2	Age AMMEAN	.309	.095	.039	-.24 .20	10.79***

*** $p < .001$

As shown in Table 5 above, there are two models for stepwise regression. Model 1 shows that Age alone explained about 5.6% of the variance in university students' achievement (FYCGPA) Model 2 shows that Age and AMMEAN together explained about 9.5%. This means that AMMEAN alone explained about 3.9% of the variance in university students' achievement (FYCGPA) and was significant ($P < .001$). Thus, model 2 was identified as the best model of regression. Mathematically, it is expressed as university students' achievement (FYCGPA) (predicted in standard score) = $-.24(\text{Age}) + .20(\text{AMMEAN})$. ASEMEAN and sex were excluded by stepwise regression.

Finding predictive validity for each of the predictor variables

In order to find answer for the last research question of the study, Table 4 was referred once again to identify the standardized regression coefficients for each of the predictor variables. Then, the relative prediction power of each of the predictor variables was determined. As can be seen in the model 3 of Table 4, all beta-values (β) are identified as statistically significant. Thus, model 3 was identified as the best model of regression. Besides, as can be evident from Table 5, AMMEAN and Age are identified as the best predictors of university students' achievement (FYCGPA) as compared to ASEMEAN and Sex/Gender.

DISCUSSION

This study was carried out on medicine and health sciences college students in Hawassa university. The total number of participants from which usable data were obtained was 208. The data gathering tools used for the study were the adapted scales of academic self-efficacy (ASE) and achievement motivation (AM). In addition, students' university achievement was measured based on first year

cumulative GPA (FYCGPA) of 4th year students who joined the university in 2020/2021 academic year. Internal consistency reliability coefficients of the two scales were found to be high, ranging from .86 - .90. Besides, validity evidences were obtained by computing bivariate correlations among the two measured constructs. Accordingly, the results yielded convergent validity evidences. Convergent and discriminant validity evidences for adapted measures were also obtained by computing inter-correlations among the two scales. Accordingly, convergent validity evidence was established based on the positive and significant correlations obtained between ASE and AM ($r = .47, p < .001$).

Generally, the findings show that the average university 4th year students have low academic self-efficacy (ASE) in the target population. In other words, the majority of the students reported low or below the average academic self-efficacy (ASE). Similarly, the findings also show that the average university 4th year students have lower-level justification or reason for joining university in the target population. On the other hand, the trends as a function of sex/gender depict that low achievement in university among 4th year students is associated more with girls than boys. The results from prior studies about the effect of gender/sex on academic achievement are mixed. For instance, the study conducted by Abd et al. (2020) showed that male and female students do not have significant differences related to their academic self-efficacy. However, according to the study of Delaney and Devereux (2021), there are consistent discrepancies between men and women's preferences for academic fields, particularly in secondary education and seem to get stronger in higher education. For example, boys are disproportionately overrepresented in STEM fields, economics, and other highly technical occupations, whereas girls are disproportionately overrepresented in nursing, teaching, and other less technical professions.

On the other hand, the growth trends of university students' achievement as a function of student age further reveals that as age increases the achievement of students decreases. This finding is not in line with the study conducted on the relationship between age and academic performance in that increase in age brings improvement in academic performance (Nasir, 2012). However, many other researchers have found that there is negative relationship between age and academic achievement (e.g. Cecilia et al., 2019; Ünal, 2019; Jabor et al.,2011).

In order to answer the research questions of the study, both standard(stepwise)and hierarchical multiple regression analyses were used. Stepwise regression analysis was used to identify the best predictors from the given predictor variables. Accordingly, AMMEAN and Age are identified as the best predictors of university students' achievement by stepwise regression analysis. Besides, hierarchical multiple regression analysis in three steps was computed. In step 1, both Age and Sex were entered purposely for they are demographic variables and were considered as bases to check the effects of major variables (ASEMEAN and AMMEAN) in this study. Then, the remaining variables were entered turn by turn. Since ASE and AM are distinct, yet related constructs, each of them was separately added respectively in steps 2 (Model II) and 3 (Model III) with Age and Sex entered in Model I. The introduction of Academic Self-Efficacy (ASE) in Model II although yielded non-significant predictive relationship with university students' achievement (FYCGPA), it has increased the overall percentage of variance at 0.1%. However, the inclusion of Achievement Motivation in Model III not only moved up the proportion of variance explained by the model with an additional variance of 5% but also increased the effect of ASE on university students' achievement (FYCGPA). Overall, university students' achievement (FYCGPA) among 4th year students is strongly predicted by students' Age, Sex, ASE, and AM contributing about 12.7% of the variance. In other words, low achievement in university students' achievement (FYCGPA)

among 4th year students is associated more with girls than boys, and students with low academic self-efficacy, and low achievement motivation. The finding of this study with respect to academic self-efficacy and achievement motivation is in line with the findings of other studies. For example, some researches and meta-analyses show that academic self-efficacy and academic performance have a well-established positive link better than other variables like cognitive ability and high school academic performance (Komarraju & Nadler, 2013; Lee, Lee, & Bong, 2014). On the other hand, past and contemporary research suggests that academic motivation is a significant non-cognitive predictor of academic performance, even better than cognitive predictors (Amrai, Motlagh, Zalani, & Parhon, 2011; Vecchione, Alessandri, & Marsicano, 2014).

Finally, in order to find answer for the last research question: “What is the predictive validity of each of the predictor variables”? the standardized regression coefficients for each of the predictor variables were identified from the last model of Table 5 in the section of findings. In regression analysis, the following prediction equation or model is often used: $Y = a + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + e$. However, for this study it is expressed as university students’ achievement (FYCGPA) (predicted in standard score) = $-.24(\text{Age}) + .13(\text{Sex}) + .15(\text{ASEMEAN}) - .25(\text{AMMEAN})$.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study, one may arrive at the following conclusions.

- University students’ achievement (FYCGPA) among 4th year students is strongly predicted by student age, sex/gender, academic self-efficacy, and achievement motivation when they are used collectively.
- Low achievement among university 4th year students is associated more with girls than boys.
- Academic self-efficacy has been emerged as non-significant predictor of university students’ achievement when used separately, but it has increased the overall percentage of variance in the model.
- When achievement motivation (AM) and academic self-efficacy (ASE) were compared in terms of relative strength, the former found to impact more on university students’ achievement than ASE.
- The growth trends of university students’ achievement as a function of students’ age reveals that as age increases the achievement of students decreases.
- Age and achievement motivation (AM) were identified to be the best predictors of university students’ achievement as compared to other variables given in this study.

Finally, the findings seem to have practical implications to concerned bodies (e.g. Policy makers, Teachers, Teacher Education Colleges, Gender officers, etc.) and further research.

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